

Trust in Action: XR Innovation, Smart Cities, and Next- Gen Networks

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What is trustworthiness?

Trustworthiness in the context of B5G and 6G networks refers to the assurance that these advanced network technologies can be relied upon to deliver secure, resilient, and high-performance communication and data services. It encompasses several key aspects:

- Security
- Reliability
- Resilience
- Privacy
- Quality of Service (QoS)
- Transparency

In essence, trustworthiness in B5G and 6G networks is about creating networks that are not only fast and efficient but also secure, reliable, and resilient to meet the ever-increasing demands of our interconnected world. COREnext explores how it can be implemented in 3 industry sectors: automotive, XR, and other verticals.

[Building Trust in the
Dynamic XR Industry:
Collaboration for End-](#)

[to-End Trustworthiness](#)

Extended reality (XR) is a catch-all term to refer to augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR). The technology is intended to combine the physical world with the “digital twin world” while being able to interact with it.

[Exploring the Advantages of Smart Cities](#)

In this article, we will address the advantages of smart city applications, which have revolutionized the way cities operate and significantly improved citizens’ quality of life. These applications leverage the power of IoT devices, data analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI) to optimize various urban operations, making cities more efficient, sustainable, and safer.

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[Safeguarding Trust and Enhancing Resilience in 5G/6G Networks](#)

The landscape of communication in the future will be shaped by the emergence of 6G technology and its architectural innovations, presenting substantial prospects for amplifying and enriching human capabilities. As we move towards the future of wireless communication, the demands on network infrastructure are becoming increasingly complex and diverse.

[Vulnerabilities Lurking](#)

[in Today's Digital World](#)

COREnext is a European-funded project to explore and enhance trustworthiness in the context of 5G and 6G technologies. But why is this so important? Let's delve into some basic vulnerabilities in today's systems and society, which COREnext aims to address.

CORENEXT

CORENEXT is an EU-funded initiative that will bring together expert stakeholders in future mobile networks and integrate their perspectives in key focus areas like digital, analogue, and integrated solutions for computing, communication, and sensing.

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